

MOUNTAIN AGRICULTURE – AN IMPORTANT ALLY OF CONSERVING BIODIVERSITY

Miruna MAIER

Centre of Mountain Economy “CE-MONT”,
Național Institute for Mountain Biotechnology,
Petreni, nr. 49, 725700, Vatra Dornei, Jud. Suceava, România

Abstract

Man and nature have been, are and will always be tightly bound to one another. This is why the conservation of biodiversity is not only an ethical objective for humanity, but also a fundamental one for safeguarding humanity’s future. Sadly, agriculture, particularly large-scale agriculture, based on maximizing the use of existing tillable fields, on using pesticides and chemical fertilizers, and on excessive use of machinery, represents a serious danger to biodiversity. In the mountain area, however, things look different. The activities of the mountain economy, through their own nature, are uniquely suited to reaching this ethical objective of humanity, the traditional agricultural practices from the mountain area having been developed in harmony with nature and not to its detriment. The result is, aside from protecting the environment, the growth of the productivity, food security and economic viability of the mountain agriculture based on small and medium-sized family farms and agro-tourism.

Keywords: *Mountain economy, biodiversity, biodiversity conservation, traditional practices, intrinsic value.*

INTRODUCTION

For a long time, one of humanity’s main issues was providing enough food for a continuously growing population. To this end, agriculture specialists have studied all the possibilities of turning their goal into reality and eliminating hunger from the planet. The results have been awe-inspiring: extensive irrigation systems in areas with little rainfall, the creation of plant and animal species more resistant to pests, diseases and harsh climatic conditions, the development of chemical fertilizers and pesticides that would maximize the production of grains, vegetables and fruit, the adoption of industrial practices that maximize the efficiency of large-scale animal husbandry, etc. However, in spite of the progress made so far, eliminating hunger remains an ephemeral dream, and the 21st century has drawn attention to the consequences that the actions taken to fulfill this dream have had on the planet, highlighting a danger that threatens all that humanity has built until now, if not the future of the human race itself.

Climate change has become an issue that can no longer be ignored. From year to year, extreme weather events severely affect agriculture, throwing the delicate balance of crops into chaos. Very high summer temperatures bring drought, and snowstorms have become a frequent visitor in the spring months, freezing the plants in the fields and greatly reducing the quantity and quality of crops.

In this context, agriculture has begun to move towards more environmentally friendly practices, designed to curb the planet’s degradation. As a result, specialists have begun to develop new methods and practices of cultivating crops and raising animals, trying to find

economically feasible solutions for transforming the large-scale industrial agriculture in plains and hilly areas into one that is efficient, sustainable and without negative consequences for the environment. However, for various reasons, they disregard the already existing solutions from a sector long ignored and marginalized in favor of the more productive plains and hilly areas: the mountain area. Poor in fertile soil and besieged by harsh climatic conditions, the mountain area is however rich in exactly what is sought-after now: traditional sustainable practices that help nature instead of destroying it, developed and perfected over hundreds of years by people born and raised there. Farming systems in mountainous areas are typically extensive, low-intensity systems, employing low-input farming practices that maintain open landscapes with a high level of biodiversity (O'Rourke et al. 2016, cited in Moreau et al. 2019) and heritage value (Bignal and McCracken 2000, cited in Moreau et al. 2019). (Moreau et al. 2019) Thus, in the race for sustainable and ecological agriculture, the mountain area has a vital advantage, having the potential to serve as a model for the plains and hilly areas, in a long-awaited and welcome role exchange.

Just as human survival depends on the environment around us, so is the survival of the planet dependent on human actions. People have a moral duty to take care of the well-being of the planet on which they live, and nowhere is this more visible than in the people of the mountains. Their diligence and strength of character have always been critical to the survival of mountain traditions and culture. Generations of mountain people grew up and lived in the mountains, in harmony with nature and the environment around them, and the farming practices they developed over time reflect this. In them shines clearly and strongly the respect for the mountain on which their prosperity depends, illuminating the symbiotic relationship between man and mountain.

METHODOLOGY

Given the nature of the paper, the research method chosen was literary review. In this sense, the first step was to search and collect texts, articles and documents on the chosen topic. The main search source was Google Scholar, using certain keywords and keyword combinations, such as: biodiversity, mountain farming, biodiversity conservation, and more. The second step was the observation, analysis and interpretation of the information within them in terms of the topic chosen for the article, making note sheets for each document studied. The third step was to organize the ideas found and present the new perspectives highlighted by them.

The literature used for the review spans a longer period of time, as the chosen topic has been of interest for a long time, not just recently.

RESULTS

1. Biodiversity conservation as an ethical objective

One of the traits that separate man from animal is man's ability to think rationally and make moral decisions, an ability that brings with it the need to respect certain moral principles and responsibilities. These differ from person to person, there is no set of moral rules and principles universally valid for all human beings, but they are invariably present in one form or another.

But is protecting other living beings one of man's moral responsibilities? The answer depends on how the problem is approached. The biocentric perspective argues that both man and animals have equal intrinsic value, showing that man has a moral duty to ensure that his actions do not harm other living beings. The anthropocentric perspective claims that the intrinsic value of man is greater than the intrinsic value of other living beings, so it does not matter from a moral standpoint whether his actions harm other beings as long as they are not to the detriment of other people.

From a deontological perspective, there are several distinct moral rules or duties. "Don't kill", "don't harm the innocent", "don't lie", "respect the rights of others" etc., are just a few examples of such rules. Observance or violation of them is inherently right or wrong, regardless of the consequences. If they are asked to justify an alleged moral rule or duty, deontologists appeal to the intrinsic value of those beings to whom it applies (Brennan and Lo 2015). For example, Tom Regan argues that animals with intrinsic value or, as he also calls it, inherent value, have a moral right to be treated with respect, which generates a general moral duty on the part of humans to not treat them as mere means to achieve other purposes. People have, first of all, a moral duty to these animals to not harm them. Thus, Regan argues, certain practices (such as hunting for sport and animal testing) violate the moral right of intrinsically valuable animals to be treated with respect. Such practices are, in his view, intrinsically wrong, regardless of the positivity or negativity of the consequences that result from them (Regan 1983, cited in Brennan and Lo 2015).

For a long time, the diversity of life on earth was considered to be one of those aspects of nature that must be protected and must be given attention and respect. Over time, several philosophers and scientists have tried to argue in favor of this concept, with varying degrees of success. John Muir, for example, used a version of Christianity in 1916 in his attempt to argue that other species deserve our respect, stating that the mere fact of being God's creation is enough for a species to have intrinsic value, even if we, as humans, can't figure out what this consists of (Muir 1916: 98–99, quoted in Brennan and Lo 2015). In spite of this, and similar observations by other writers in the first decades of the 20th century, sustainability and sustainable development did not become central to environmental policy until the 1980s, when biodiversity began to be studied by biologists and ecosystem theorists, but without being a main concern for them. Despite this, a significant number of books and papers by biologists and philosophers have attempted to give a warning regarding the loss of species and the possible impact of these losses on ecosystem functions, including a decline in its moral and economic value as a consequence of the decrease of natural variety (Norton 1986 and 1987, Wilson 1992, cited in Brennan and Lo 2015).

The work of scientists and philosophers in this field contributed to the publication, in 1992, of the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity, the preamble of which explicitly refers to both the usefulness of nature and its intrinsic value, combining themes from economics and philosophy. According to the Convention, the contracting parties are aware "of the intrinsic value of biological diversity and of the ecological, genetic, social, economic, scientific, educational, cultural, recreational and aesthetic values of biological diversity and its components" (UN 1992: 1). They are also "conscious of the importance of biological diversity for evolution and for maintaining life sustaining systems of the biosphere" (UN 1992: 1).

But how should biodiversity be measured? And, whatever way it's measured, what does an area's biodiversity reveal about its value? These two questions are at the heart of

contemporary discussions about biodiversity. To these questions can be added another one: do conservation ethics place a specific emphasis on the conservation of wildlife as such or at least on natural landscapes and populations? Let's not forget that high biodiversity, through some measures, can be associated with human use and occupation, like for example adding an agricultural system to a desert, which increases local diversity. Therefore, not all natural systems maximize biodiversity when unaffected by human influence (Brennan and Lo 2015). Similarly, in some forest systems in the temperate area, disturbances in the forest (including through land clearing activities) causes an increase in tree species diversity (Brennan 2014: 92–108, cited in Brennan and Lo 2015). On the other hand, many highly prized wilderness areas are not particularly rich in natural variety (Sarkar 2005: 21–44, cited in Brennan and Lo 2015). This doesn't mean that there aren't any places where wildlife and biodiversity are truly closely linked, such as in protected wilderness areas which are also biodiversity hotspots. Undoubtedly, biodiversity management and conservation is easier in areas where the human population has a low density (Mittermeier et al. 2003, cited in Brennan and Lo 2015). However, in spite of that, biodiversity protection is a completely different issue from wildlife conservation (Brennan and Lo 2015).

Unfortunately, the fact that there is still no single agreed method of measuring biodiversity (Maier 2012: 115–20, cited in Brennan and Lo 2015) complicates matters regarding policies on the number and diversity of species (Brennan and Lo 2015). Other factors that aggravate the issue of measuring biodiversity are measuring ecosystem stability and biological productivity, which generate their own issues (Sarkar 2005: 106–44, cited in Brennan and Lo 2015). Some authorities have considered that the existence of high levels of biodiversity is correlated with systemic productivity and high stability, a point of view in clear contradiction with the observation that many of the world's most productive systems are not very rich in species. The last decade, however, has brought some consensus that systems with moderate biodiversity have high productivity and that increasing diversity within these systems can be helpful against external disruptions that often lead to reduced productivity (deLaplante and Picasso 2011, cited in Brennan and Lo 2015). Thus, conservation and rehabilitation efforts would be best concentrated on whole systems, not on individual populations, what matters being not so much the defense or restoration of individual species, but safeguarding groups of species that form landscape and forest systems (Brennan and Lo 2015) and whose existence maintains the delicate balance of the ecosystems they are a part of.

The strongest arguments for conserving biodiversity are, for humans, above all ethical, not those based on its usefulness to human beings. Let us not forget that the ecosystems that satisfy a large number of human preferences are provided by low-diversity agricultural systems in which food is produced (Norton 1988, cited in Brennan and Lo 2015). Nowadays, many endangered species have already become only marginally functional for the ecosystem in which they are found, giving the opportunity to someone who takes a purely cost-benefit perspective to argue that the negative impact of those species' deaths on system productivity could be negligible or even acceptable in anthropocentric terms, as the resources that would be needed to conserve or restore the populations of those species could be used to promote human benefits in other ways (Brennan and Lo 2015).

So is biodiversity an intrinsically valuable asset that deserves to be protected as an end in itself, regardless of the instrumental values it may or may not have for humans?

(Brennan and Lo 2015) The answer seems to be yes. In most cases, people prefer to have a variety of things they like instead of having more of one thing they like, which is also true of values. If we assume that people generally prefer a set of good things of different kinds rather than a larger collection of good things of the same kind, and that this preference for diversity in good things can survive the test of time, it turns out that diversity in good things is a good thing in itself. Thus, if we accept the biocentric moral perspective that every form of life is intrinsically valuable, it is natural and correct to accept the additional proposition that biodiversity is also something intrinsically valuable. In other words, if life is a good thing and if a world containing good things of many different kinds is better than a world containing good things of fewer kinds, then greater biodiversity is better than less biodiversity (Brennan and Lo 2015).

For some people, however, it's inconceivable that biodiversity could be important for a very simple reason: they can't imagine that another species could have any intrinsic value independent of its relationship with humans. In their view, man is the supreme being, and the value of other things or species derives from how useful it is to humans. Consequently, biodiversity is important only insofar as it is useful to the human species.

Faced with this doubt whether every living thing, regardless of species, is truly valuable in itself, we can simply answer with another question: what good reasons do we have to say that the members of the human species have an intrinsic value greater than the members of other species on Earth? (Brennan and Lo 2015).

Most of the arguments in favor of the view that the intrinsic value of the human species is significantly greater, if not exclusive to it, have certain similarities. They appeal to the fact that humans have certain unique traits, such as self-awareness, rationality, the ability to speak and write, to make moral decisions, to create and appreciate aesthetics, etc. These characteristics are purely human; they aren't found in any other life form on Earth or are found only in a much smaller degree compared to man. Hence the idea that because these traits are the most valuable and morally relevant, the creatures that possess them to a greater extent have a higher intrinsic value than the creatures that possess them to a lesser extent or in which they are lacking completely. However, this argument starts from a faulty premise, the set of traits identified and assumed to be the worthiest and most morally relevant being exactly those traits that are characteristic and commonly possessed by members of our own species (Taylor 1986, Plumwood 1993, quotes in Brennan and Lo 2015). This subjective premise, which looks at everything in terms of the idea that the traits that separate man from other species are superior to the traits that separate other species from man, is not fair to other life forms, being unable to ever lead to an objective assessment of the intrinsic value of any other species, which are disadvantaged from the beginning.

If we eliminate the idea of human superiority, we can make, at most, objective comparisons of different individuals of the same species in terms of the specific merits of their species. For example, we can compare the ability of a cat to catch mice with the ability of another cat to catch mice, or the ability of a chamois to climb sheer slopes with that of another chamois to climb sheer slopes. But in the absence of a single standard of "good life" applicable to all species, we cannot conceptually compare the skills of individuals belonging to different species. By what criteria would we judge whether a cat that has the abilities and skills to live a good cat life is better than a chamois that has the abilities and skills to live a good chamois life? The same argument applies to the supposed superiority of human

beings. It makes no sense to say that a human being that has the capacity and abilities to lead a good human life is better than another being that has the capacity and abilities to lead a good life in rapport to its own species (Brennan and Lo 2015).

If the appeal to human superiority is the only line of defense that people have in trying to morally justify the exploitation of the environment and its other inhabitants, and given that people have already benefited disproportionately from the suffering and damage caused by their actions to members of other species, it's logical that the responsibility to prove that they are indeed "better" than the rest is also on humans (Brennan and Lo 2015). If man is indeed a morally superior animal and the greatness of humanity is not mere human self-magnification, then man has a moral and ethical duty to ensure that his actions do not hurt other beings. In order to truly be called a moral animal, he must show a moral ability to look beyond his own interests and those of his loved ones and show his willingness to care for and share what he has with those who are less able to make it on their own. Thus, the conservation of biodiversity is a very important moral responsibility for humans.

2. Mountain economy and biodiversity conservation

Despite the importance of biodiversity conservation in Europe, it is still being lost at an alarming rate. One of the main factors leading to the loss of biodiversity is economic activity, in particular through habitat destruction, climate change, the introduction of invasive species, overexploitation and pollution.

Agriculture and biodiversity have always been closely linked, with mutual and complex interactions between them. Thus, agriculture needs biodiversity at the same time as it influences it, this being the basis of agricultural production. On one hand, biodiversity is the origin of all crops and domestic animals and their variety. On the other hand, the components of wild biodiversity in agricultural and associated landscapes form ecosystems that are essential for agricultural production. The agricultural sector is thus one of the main industries based on natural resources that can provide benefits to biodiversity through the application of sustainable management systems and the adoption of alternative and innovative technologies and practices. Unfortunately, agriculture, through the methods it uses (dedicating large areas of land to a single species, overgrazing, usage of pesticides and chemical fertilizers, excessive mechanization), often has a devastating effect on biodiversity.

Mountain farming is uniquely suited to biodiversity conservation. Mountain agriculture has been declared of capital importance by the European Union (EU) and governments of several countries with a long-standing tradition of protecting their agricultural sector. Multiple agricultural and environmental policies have been established to support economic activities in mountains and farmers' role in biodiversity conservation. However, the effects of some EU environmental policies may have been counterproductive in preventing, and perhaps redressing the trends of land and farm abandonment observed since the 1970s (Hinojosa et al. 2018).

Traditionally, mountain farming is, through its own nature, focused on small and medium-sized farms, the practices used in them, developed and used for centuries, being designed in such a way as to work with nature, not against it to the detriment of other species. An example would be the maintenance of a quality polyflora in mountain meadows and pastures, one of the cornerstones of mountain agriculture, vital for maintaining food security. Incidentally, achieving sustainable food security is a critical goal for small holder farmers in mountainous regions around the world (Adelabu et al. 2020).

In recent years, studies have shown that the decline in the number of birds and butterflies on agricultural land and the lesser diversity of plant species are linked to increased use of agricultural land. At the same time, they also show that a large number of wildlife species and semi-natural habitat types in Europe depend on the existence and continued use of low-intensity agricultural practices.

Unfortunately, in the last century, traditional European extended land use systems, which can ensure the maintenance of semi-natural grasslands, have changed significantly, a matter of particular concern for the mountain regions where the low soil fertility and the thin fertile soil layer (10–20 cm) means a lower production and a significantly higher labor cost than in the fertile plains and hilly areas. As a result, mountain farming is focusing more and more on highly productive and/or more convenient semi-natural grasslands, while unfavorable areas are abandoned, leading, over time, to the homogenization of the landscape and to the disappearance of microhabitats. The abandonment of less productive pastures usually leads to their rapid invasion by the forest, shrubs and plant species with low forage value, as well as to a drastic decrease in the size of the semi-natural grasslands, which in turn leads to a significant decrease in species diversity and the loss of polyflora with high forage value (Babai and Molnár, 2013).

This abandonment is driven by the economic and demographic changes taking place at local and regional level, and is also encouraged by some agro-environmental subsidy schemes, their extreme bureaucracy and the strict milk production regulations implemented by the European Union (Babai and Molnár, 2013).

In recent years, research in the field of biodiversity conservation revealed that more and more researchers are of the opinion that in order to maintain biodiversity, biological factors sometimes fall in second place in importance compared to social and psychological factors. In this context, research on ecological knowledge systems, ecological behavior, motivation and incorporation in human communities where traditional landscape patterns and large areas of semi-natural pastures with a high diversity of plant species, insects and birds are still preserved, is especially important.

Traditionally, ecological knowledge consists of a combination of elements of theory, practical experience and beliefs. In Europe, traditional ecological knowledge is based on decades of experience with the living landscape. This experience has been hard earned over the centuries via ecological experiences gained through practical management of landscapes, experiences belonging not to a single individual, but to communities, and which are more connected to the rituals of social life than to Western science (Babai and Molnár, 2013). Unfortunately, today this collective knowledge is on the verge of extinction, which would be a severe blow to biodiversity conservation efforts. It's no secret that this traditional ecological knowledge is very important for understanding the links between ecological and social systems, and for developing more effective and efficient policies for the biodiversity and landscape conservation, and with them all the elements related to biodiversity conservation.

Current agricultural policies focus on maximizing the use of existing agricultural land, ignoring both the specificity of the mountain area and its traditional ecological knowledge, with the predictable result of considerably weakening the strong traditional links between man and nature in traditional rural landscapes. It is a worrying situation for the survival of biodiversity in the mountain area, which relies heavily on maintaining local ecological knowledge and preserving traditional land use systems, so important for maintaining the richness of species in mountain meadows.

Additionally, Romania finds itself in a more delicate context than Western countries, due in no small part to its past under a communist regime, which gave rise to unique issues. The main challenges for the post-communist countries lies in their capacity to: (i) access complementary funds for nature conservation, beside their inadequate annual budget for nature conservation, assured by the governments; (ii) harmonize the policy implementation between nature conservation and agriculture; (iii) bridge the gaps between science, practice and policy by continuous knowledge transfer between research, farmers, conservationist and employee of public institutions, politicians; and (iv) address regional, often local problems (Balázs 2018).

CONCLUSIONS

From both a moral and a pragmatic standpoint, man has a duty and a responsibility to protect biodiversity, since as biodiversity plays an important role in agriculture, understanding the interactions between biodiversity and agricultural production and putting this knowledge into practice is essential to ensure not only a stable, safe and high supply of high quality, safe and sufficient food products, but also the protection of the environment, which benefits the entire planet.

Among the general benefits that the presence of high biodiversity brings are: increased productivity, food security and economic profitability; the reduction of the pressure on agriculture on areas with a delicate ecological balance, forests and endangered species; an increase of the stability and sustainability of agricultural systems, especially small-scale ones; the diversification of food products and income-generating opportunities for farmers, especially in small and medium-sized farms; and the maximization of the efficient use of natural resources and the environment.

As regards agricultural productivity, efforts to conserve biodiversity result in a more effective management of natural pests and diseases, the conservation of soil and an increased fertility for it, an improved pollination of plants and trees, the protection of soil and water, and so on. This ensures the production of high-quality, food products with added value, as well as an increased resistance to disturbance or climate change and a much easier adaptation of agricultural production systems' capacity to them.

Biodiversity conservation doesn't only benefit agriculture, but also society, such as through a reduced impact of agricultural practices on the environment, the conservation of plant, animal and wild insect species, maintaining the aesthetics of natural landscapes, improving human nutrition, ensuring safe sources of natural medicines and essential vitamins, as well as a significant mitigation of greenhouse gas emissions, one of the main culprits in global warming (EU Business and Biodiversity Platform, no date).

Also, a crucial set of questions must be kept in mind when discussing biodiversity conservation policy: should the objective be to restore biodiversity, to conserve already existing biodiversity, or even further increase biodiversity on certain land parcels, at the scale of the farm, or even at the scale of a territory or a region? (Wezel et al. 2018) To date, there has not been a consensus regarding these questions, at any level.

In the mountain area, the interest in conserving valuable biodiversity is apparent in everything from traditional agricultural practices to cultural and social traditions, developed and preserved over the centuries. To this end, the ecological knowledge of local farmers is of particular importance, just as the local social structures play a vital role in the resilience

of small-scale mountain farming. In a recent study, interviewed livestock farmers expressed their sense of responsibility to maintaining the mountain landscape. The expansion of shrubs and forests was negatively perceived as the symbolic representation of their failure to maintain the pastures that they inherited from their predecessors (Barnaud and Couix, 2020).

That is why it is vital, for the survival of society and even the human species, that the mountain economy and its policies do everything possible to protect the valuable species in this area so important for our country. And we mustn't forget that, to support biodiversity-friendly land-use and management practices, practitioners – in our case, farmers – need information and feedback about how their management practice influences biodiversity (Tasser et al. 2019).

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